

The Function That Grows randomly that you can make

Definition: For each natural number y , define $f(y) = z(\uparrow^x n)$, where n is the least natural number such that the decimal expansion of $z(\uparrow^x n)$ has the first y digits of a positive real number in the exact places:

Where z is a real number greater than or equal to zero
 u, t, o, \dots and so on.. are whole numbers

Units digit = u

Tenths digit = t

Hundredths digit = o

...and so on for y digits.

If you decide to make your own function out of this
some may grow extremely fast

some maybe undefined eg: $(u.to...=4.00.... z=10$ then no matter the value of $x=1$ then no matter what y 's value it will be undefined) or it could even be a small number You can also include tens and hundreds and thousands..... Etc. places

Example: let $z=(\pi+1)$ and $x=1$
and u.to... Be the the digits of π

Definition: For each natural number y , define $f(y) = (\pi+1)^n$, where n is the least natural number such that the decimal expansion of $(\pi+1)^n$ has the first y digits of π in the exact places

Units digit = 3

Tenths digit = 1

Hundredths digit = 4

$f(1)=(\pi+1)^{29}$

Example 2: let $z=(\pi+1)$ and $x=2$
and u.to... Be the the digits of π

Definition: For each natural number y , define $f(y) = (\pi+1) \uparrow \uparrow n$, where n is the least natural number such that the decimal expansion of $(\pi+1) \uparrow \uparrow n$ has the first y digits of π in the exact places

Units digit = 3

Tenths digit = 1

Hundredths digit = 4

$f(1)$ is huge and I failed to calculate

This is random growth (if π is normal) that means at certain n for both functions could $f(n) > \text{tree}(n)$ but it's hypothetical

So this is my theorem on this randomly growing function.